

SPATIAL PLANNING IN THE REPUBLIC OF CROATIA

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Abstract: *Spatial planning is one of the foundations for the development of an area, city or municipality, county or the entire state. It ensures the conditions for the use (management), protection, and governance of the territory of the Republic of Croatia, including its exclusive economic zone, as a particularly valuable and limited national asset. In doing so, it provides prerequisites for social and economic development, environmental and nature protection, quality construction, and rational use of natural and cultural resources. In Croatia, spatial planning is conducted based on legislation and regulations, in digital form via the Spatial Planning Information System (ISPU). This paper provides an overview of spatial plans and their transition to a new spatial planning system in the Republic of Croatia, which will enable faster development of individual new ISPU modules aimed at implementing key goals such as greater transparency, urban rehabilitation, urban land consolidation, establishment of new planning measures, and more.*

Keywords: *Spatial planning, ISPU, new generation spatial plans*

1. INTRODUCTION

Spatial planning provides the conditions for the use, protection, and governance of the territory of the Republic of Croatia, recognized as a particularly valuable and limited national good. It supports the prerequisites for social and economic development, environmental and nature protection, high-quality construction, and the rational use of natural and cultural resources (URL 1).

The goals of spatial planning include: balanced spatial development aligned with economic, social, and environmental frameworks, spatial sustainability regarding rational use and conservation of spatial capacities on land, sea, and seabed for effective spatial protection (NN 153/2013). Cross-border influences are taken into account, linking Croatia with European spatial planning systems while fostering and developing regional spatial characteristics. Special attention is given to the harmonious distribution of human activities in space for functional and sustainable community development, the protection of integral spatial values, reasonable use and conservation of natural assets, nature protection, and pollution risk prevention. Cultural and other significant assets enjoy special protection ensured through spatial plans.

Successful spatial planning involves well-organized land use, high-quality and humane development of urban and rural settlements, and a safe, healthy, and socially functional living and working environment. It also encompasses the integrity of valuable coastal ecosystems, sea quality, adequate transport systems (especially public transport), accessibility to services, and inclusive urban design for children, elderly, and persons with disabilities. Design quality and spatial aesthetics, high-value built environments, and respect for natural and urban landscapes and heritage, especially tourism development areas, are core components. Planning also addresses economic development, national security, and protection from natural and other disasters. Spatial planning goals are achieved through applying planning principles during plan preparation, adoption, and implementation (NN 153/2013).

Spatial planning is based on principles of integrated approaches, scientifically and professionally verified facts, sustainable development, public and private interest protection, horizontal and vertical integration, and public access to data and documents relevant to spatial planning (NN 153/2013).

2. SPATIAL PLANNING

As an interdisciplinary activity, spatial planning is both an institutional and technical framework for managing the spatial dimension of sustainability. It is based on the assessment of: (1) development potentials respecting spatial identity, (2) space protection requirements, and (3) environmental and nature quality preservation. It defines land uses, development conditions for activities and infrastructure, spatial allocation, urban renewal conditions, and procedures for implementing planned interventions (NN 153/2013). These elements align with the classical definition of effective spatial planning as an institutional function of development governance (Faludi, 2000).

In Croatia, spatial planning is implemented at several levels, producing various plans: the State Spatial Development Plan (DPPR), Special Area Plans (PPPPO), State-level Urban Development Plans (UPU), County Spatial Plans (PPŽ), the City of Zagreb Spatial Plan (PPGZ), County-level Urban Development Plans, and Municipal/City Spatial Plans (PPUO/PPUG), General Urban Development Plans (GUP), and Urban Development Plans (UPU) (NN 153/2013).

Plan preparation begins with the Spatial Development Strategy of the Republic of Croatia, adopted by the Ministry and confirmed by the Croatian Parliament. Lower-level plans must align with higher-level ones. Each plan includes implementation provisions (legal regulations), a graphic component (maps), and explanatory text (analysis, goals, and rationale).

2.1. "Old" Generation Plans

Prior to the new Regulation (NN 152/2023), spatial plans were prepared according to the 1998 Regulation (NN 106/1998). Plans consisted of a textual component in .doc format and graphic elements created in CAD software, printed, signed, and sealed. Approval required multiple signatories, including local mayors or county prefects. The process consumed significant energy, resources (paper and ink), and time. Data access was difficult, analyses cumbersome, and inconsistencies arose due to differing projections (Gauss-Krueger zones 5 and 6) and non-unified cartographic symbology. These issues prompted the transition to the ISPU system.

2.2. "New" Generation Plans – Spatial Planning Information System (ISPU)

With the adoption of the new Regulation on Spatial Plans (NN 152/2023) on January 1st, 2024, spatial planning entered a new phase. This digital transformation, developed over several years, is recognized as a major innovation in Croatian spatial governance (Janković & Tomić, 2019). ISPU enables plan preparation, adoption, implementation, oversight, spatial monitoring, and reporting in digital form. It integrates systems from various public bodies producing or maintaining spatial data.

Figure 1: ISPU

This architecture ensures compliance with the INSPIRE Directive principles on spatial data infrastructures in the EU (Nebert & Vretanos, 2007). ISPU is managed electronically and uses the official Croatian coordinate system. (Image 1).

ISPU includes data on land use, property ownership, existing and draft spatial plans, land use designations, legal and physical planning conditions, construction permits, usage, demolition, and sectoral policies and documents.

Authorities must provide all relevant spatial data through ISPU, which is publicly accessible.

Figure 2: ISPU modules

ISPU contains 15 modules; the most relevant for planning are ePlans and ePlans Editor (Image 2). These support both the development of new plans and the transformation of analogue plans. Planners define the scope, assign roles, manage public consultations, and adopt plans within the system. Editing occurs in ePlans Editor, linking vector graphics and text. Plans may also be prepared in compatible software ensuring spatial-textual linkage (NN 153/2013).

Plans are verified for topology and compliance, then transferred into ePlans for adoption. The adoption decision is generated from ePlans Editor data and templates. The legend is auto-generated, and metadata ensures clarity. A digital plan dossier (PDF) is created for publication (NN 153/2013).

2.3. Data Transformation

All analogue spatial plans in raster form have been imported into ISPU. These were mainly CAD-based with symbology defined by the 1998 regulation (Image 3). Due to inconsistencies, overlapping plans, and outdated projections (HDKS), transformation into vector format is required. This ensures better integration and alignment between neighboring plans. Transformation occurs within ePlans similarly to new plan creation but skips certain steps since plans are already in force.

After transformation, old generation data provides a reliable basis for new plans. Combined with statistical and registry data, transformed plans support enhanced spatial analysis and decision-making.

Figure 3: ISPU – "Old" Generation Plan

3. ISPU MODULES AND TOOL FOR THE PUBLIC

The registry of all spatial plans, those in-force and the outdated ones, old and new generation ones, can be found using the eCatalogue module of ISPU.

By searching for in-force plans made after January 1st, 2024, through the eCatalogue module, over 7.200 results were obtained in July 2025. Some of those results are related to translated plans while others to modified

or completely new ones. As Croatia has allocated funds for the translation of old generation plans, this number is expected to grow rapidly in the coming years. There are numerous filtering options available, and a search bar, allowing users to easily navigate to their area of interest, and to inspect the plans. It is simply a matter of clicking on one of the search results to pan and zoom to the desired location (image 4). Clicking on the arrow button within the result allows users to access data on the plan itself, and its provisions (image 5). The module makes spatial plans easily accessible to the public from any place, at any time.

Figure 4: eCatalogue module search for new generation spatial plans

Figure 5: Accessing data and provisions of the spatial plan

Another tool useful to the public is the location information tool (Croatian “Lokacijska informacija”) that can be found within the main ISPU interface. By clicking on the button, a window pops up where different selection methods and types of information to be found can be chosen. Once the location has been confirmed, the requested search data and easy access to it is provided in the pop-up window. The example of one such search is given in image 6 where the search entails acquisition of information of plans that are in-force for the selected point location.

Figure 6: Location tool application

A user also has an option to manually inspect different areas of interest, use the main toolbar (on the left), find the plans in the Spatial plan registry, and display its different thematic information on the map. One can view the basic distribution of intended uses, infrastructure systems, and special provisions if there are any for the area. The user only needs to use the appropriate zoom level for each plan to display it as local, regional and national level plans are visible on different level scales.

Figure 7: Basic manual inspection of spatial plans

4. CONCLUSION

Spatial plans function as by-laws, requiring clarity and uniformity for legal certainty. Through ISPU and plan transformation, transparency and consistency have improved. All data processed via ePlans Editor follow Croatia's official coordinate system (HTRS96/TM), using standardized regulations and nomenclature. Data is publicly available.

ISPU simplifies access to spatial data and planning regulations, promotes interpretative consistency, and enhances legal certainty for all stakeholders.

Further system improvements are enabled by technological advances, better registry management, and widespread digital literacy. The development of individual new modules of the ISPU system will help in the implementation of key goals such as greater transparency, urban rehabilitation, urban consolidation, the establishment of new planning measures, and more. Planned upgrades include integration with eCitizens to

promote public participation in planning, aligning with European practices of web-based public GIS participation (Kingston et al., 2000). The new eRegimes module will streamline planning and provide instant spatial information.

Future development includes 3D data (digital twins), artificial intelligence support, and continued user-driven module enhancements. Digital twins are becoming essential tools for dynamic urban system modeling and analysis (Batty, 2018).

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